

INTRODUCTION TO SPECIAL ISSUE

‘Administrative Study in Sulawesi Selatan, Indonesia.’*

The special issue of *Gnosi Journal: An Academic Journal of Human Theory and Praxis* features a subset of papers written by researchers within the field of public administration in the South Sulawesi province of Indonesia. This special issue explicated on some important issues germane to both the ‘private’ and ‘public’ organisations within the South Sulawesi province of Indonesia.

Organization study is important because it helps humans to learn more about the meaning of a work process, be it formal or non-formal organizations. It is worth noting that an organization is identical to an individual, a structured and systematic group of individuals who are members of a system. An organization also consists of various groups that have common interests to achieve specific goals together. This is because humans are social creatures who are sure to interact with others. By working with others, the division of labour is imminent and the workload on individuals will be greatly reduced. Thus, by engaging in an organizational study, the strength and lacunas within the studied organization will be revealed. The organizational study can also help leaders and decision-makers within an organization promote values such as accountability, transparency, effectiveness, and efficiency; the skills required for effective governance; the mobilization and/or incentivization of staff; and, broadly, the ability of organisations to achieve their policy goals. An organizational study can also help members within an organization to learn to express opinions and the feedbacks are vital for the organization’s improvement.

In the special issue, seven (7) papers were accepted and published. The first paper by Jamaluddin *et al.*, described the effectiveness of the application of the situational leadership style among members at the PT Singosari Timur Jaya Makassar. The second study by Muh Nasrullah *et al.*, tried to determine how the use of work facilities affect the performance of employees at the Office of Investment and One-Stop Services, Gowa Regency. The third study by Muhammad Darwis *et al.*, tried to determine the implementation of professionalism of the administrative workforce at SMK Country 7 Bulukumba. The fourth study by Muhammad Darwis *et al.* showed the effect of the Principal’s leadership role on teacher’s performance, as well as an analysis of the teacher’s performance at the Tonra 1 Tonra District Bone School Bone Regency of the South Sulawesi Province, Indonesia. The fifth study by Nirwana *et al.* analyzed the employee performance appraisal at the Bone and Transmigration Office of the District of Bone. The sixth study by Sirajuddin Saleh *et al.* describes the effectiveness of class management in class X students at Vocational high School (Indonesia: *Sekolah Menengah Kejuruan / SMK*) Country 1 Maros. And lastly, the seventh study by Sirajuddin Saleh *et al.*, determine

the effect of academic supervision on increasing the pedagogic competence of MAN (*Madrasah Aliah Negeri/Indonesia*) Jenepono teachers.

The papers published in this special issue reflect the persistence custom of Public Administration inquiry and how it continues to help create new academic knowledge, by synergising theory and practice into unique understandings. It is important to note that, theoretical advances cannot be made without allusion to practice; although studies that seek to explore and understand how practitioners understand their world cannot be merely descriptive anecdotes but require theoretical coherence informed by rigorous empirical evidence.

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